

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.2.6
Deliverable title	Project-internal CO ₂ emissions report
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
Deliverable Lead authors	Mario L. Salinas, Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)
Deliverable Contributors	Amal Salhi (CMCC)
Deliverable due date	2022-06-30
Deliverable latest review date	2022-09-05
Comments	

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary2

2. Introduction2

3. Data and Methods.....3

 3.1 The collection form.....3

 3.2 The CO₂ estimation.....4

 3.3. Data processing.....6

4. Results7

 4.1 Overall statistics.....7

 4.2 Transportation means.....8

 4.3. Partners and Events.....8

5. Conclusions11

Bibliography12

Appendix A.....12

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports about the process of monitoring the carbon footprint of GUTTA project travels. It is meant to raise awareness within the project partnership about how travelling choices affected their CO₂ emissions. Both the assessment methodology and its numerical outcomes are described in this report. It includes travels since the project proposal preparation meeting in 2017 till the project's end in 2022. The total travel-related emissions were estimated to be above 11.5 tons CO₂. This roughly corresponds to the carbon footprint of an Italian citizen along two years. The most used transportation means for GUTTA travels was plane, followed by car. Ferry and train, albeit the most emission-efficient means, were used for over 13% of the total distance, accounting for just 5% of the total emissions.

2. Introduction

As part of Activity 1.2 “Day-to-day project management, coordination, and internal communication” of the GUTTA project, its Application Form reads:

“In view of the specific contribution of GUTTA to environmental sustainability, PPs will commit themselves to report to the LP their estimated CO₂ emissions due to travels for internal project meetings and project related events (e.g. it will be possible to use carbon footprint calculators such as <http://calculator.carbonfootprint.com/calculator.aspx?tab=3>). This will raise the partnership's awareness of her environmental impact and the high ethical meaning of their project activities for the Programme area and beyond.”

Abiding to this, the LP developed a methodology for monitoring the carbon footprint of GUTTA project travels and ensured it was applied by all PPs. The data collected were then automatically processed for extracting statistically relevant conclusions.

This document reports both the data collection method in Sect.3 and its outcomes in Sect.4. The conclusions and future recommendations can be found in Sect.5. Some aggregated information from the collected dataset is shared in Appendix A.

The shortcuts used along the document refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3667198

3. Data and Methods

This section illustrates how the data was gathered and processed.

3.1 The collection form

In the first months of the GUTTA project, the LP defined a template for reporting CO₂ emissions of travels. It consisted in a multi-sheet Excel file as shown in Figure 1.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Name	NAME							
2	Surname	SURNAME							
3	Affiliation	AFFILIATION							
4									
5	Voyage	A - B - C - D - C - E - F - A							
6	Number of voyage legs	7							
7									
8									
9	voyage leg #	date	transportation mean	distance [km]	correction_factor	CO2			
10				http://maps.google.com		https://www.carbonfootprint.com/calculator.aspx			
11									
12	1	24/04/17	train	613		0.02			
13	2	24/04/17	ferry	244		0.10			
14	3	27/04/17	bus	158		0.02			
15	4	29/04/17	bus	158		0.02			
16	5	29/04/17	plane	405		0.05			
17	6	29/04/17	plane	480		0.07			
18	7	29/04/17	bus	39		0.00			

Figure 1: Screenshot of the CO₂ emission report template sheet referred to the voyage in Figure 2. This sheet refers to a person named “NAME” reporting, for each voyage leg, the date, mean of transport, distance, car occupation correction factor, and CO₂ emission estimate.

A file was filled for each GUTTA project partner organisation (PP) with each sheet referring to a specific travelling person, attending a specific event. Guests invited to attend project events (such as the KOM or the final workshop) were collectively considered as an extra organization. For each event, each PP had to provide a file according to the template of Fig.1 and filled with information regarding its travelling employees. In the form, each travel was recorded starting from its itinerary. This consisted in “legs”, joining the locations (or nodes) at which a switch in transport means occurred.

Figure 2: Example of voyage map corresponding to the data provided in Fig.1. The full itinerary A-B-C-D-C-E-F-A is made up of six directed legs (A-B, B-C, C-D, D-E, E-F, F-A).

For instance, in reference to both Figure 1 and Figure 2, a traveler started his voyage by train from Lecce to Ancona (first leg) then switched to a ferry sailing from Ancona to Split (second leg), then took a bus from Split to Zadar (third leg) and, after his stay in Zadar for a project meeting, took a bus back from Zadar to Split (fourth leg), from where he flew to Rome (fifth leg) and then to Brindisi (sixth leg), getting back to Lecce via bus (seventh leg).

The PPs were requested to provide this type of information through the standard collection forms displayed in Figure 1.

3.2 The CO₂ estimation

The LP then first manually completed the forms by estimating the CO₂ emissions of each individual leg. To this end, the following set of rules was used:

- the distance was computed via Google Maps for all transportation means but for ferries, for which the length of the maritime route was estimated from a dedicated service¹
- for car voyages only, the car occupancy was considered, corresponding to the number of people that shared the car trips
- CO₂ emissions were estimated via a publicly available carbon footprint calculator², but for the means of transport mentioned in the following bullet
- for car and ferry legs the formula was used:

$$CO_2 = cDIST_{tm} * distance$$
 where $cDIST_{tm}$ is the carbon intensity indicator related to transport mean tm . For cars, a constant value of 200 g CO₂/km was used throughout, while for ferries the value of this indicator was taken from the THETIS-MRV database³, see next bullet.
- Emission intensity data for ferries vessels sailing in European seas are shown in Table 1.

THETIS-MRV version		2018-v217	2019-v191	2020-v62	2021-v5
Vessel	IMOn	Emission intensity [g CO ₂ / km/ pax]			
Aurelia	7602120	767	351	1,277	1,364
Dubrovnik	7615048	4	3	29	8
Marko Polo	7230599	5	2	12	8
Zadar	9021485	1	1	1	1
All ferries in EEA		1,279	1,068	2,059	1,475

Table 1: CO₂ emission intensities of some ferries during 2018-2021 (according to the dataset versions reported after the year). Just non-high speed crafts are considered for the EEA mean values.

The Aurelia carbon intensity was in all years much higher than the Marko Polo's one, (another ferry sailing on the Ancona-Split route). However, it was below the average of the ferry fleet sailing in the European Economic Area (EEA). Furthermore, it is seen that the values of this carbon intensity indicator strongly fluctuated in time across years 2018-2021. This reflects the fact that per-passenger carbon intensity depends on the actual occupation of the vessels. The latter strongly fluctuated given that the growth trend 2018-19 was interrupted in 2020 by the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic.

¹ <http://ports.com/sea-route/>

² <http://calculator.carbonfootprint.com/calculator.aspx?tab=3>

³ THETIS-MRV corresponds to the data collected through the EU-MRV system and published on <https://mrv.emsa.europa.eu/> by EMSA

3.3. Data processing

Once the data collection was completed, a data processing phase followed. It included:

- Data cleaning (e.g.: unifying transport means and affiliation names)
- Adding new columns: leg date and voyage destination

The resulting dataset included one row for each voyage leg and traveler. An example is shown in GUTTA_D126_CO2

voyage_dest	leg_date	affiliation	leg_num	leg_voyage	transp_mean	ferry_IMOn	car_occupancy	distance [km]	CO2 [tons]
Zadar	201704	CMCC	1	Lecce - Ancona	train			613	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	2	Ancona - Split	ferry	7602120		243.7	0.101
Zadar	201704	CMCC	3	Split - Zadar	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	4	Zadar - Spit	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	5	Spit - Rome	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	6	Rome - Brindisi	plane			480	0.07
Zadar	201704	CMCC	7	Brindisi - Lecce	bus			42.6	0
Zadar	201704	CMCC	1	Lecce - Rome	train			580	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	2	Rome - Split	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	3	Split - Zadar	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	4	Zadar - Spit	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	5	Spit - Rome	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	6	Rome - Brindisi	plane			480	0.07
Zadar	201704	CMCC	7	Brindisi - Lecce	bus			42.6	0

Table 2: Example of some entries in the consolidated dataset. The emitted CO2 is given in tons and the distance in km, while the car_occupancy field is empty since the reported transport mean for this specific leg was not a car.

GUTTA_D126_CO2

voyage_dest	leg_date	affiliation	leg_num	leg_voyage	transp_mean	ferry_IMOn	car_occupancy	distance [km]	CO2 [tons]
Zadar	201704	CMCC	1	Lecce - Ancona	train			613	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	2	Ancona - Split	ferry	7602120		243.7	0.101
Zadar	201704	CMCC	3	Split - Zadar	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	4	Zadar - Spit	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	5	Spit - Rome	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	6	Rome - Brindisi	plane			480	0.07
Zadar	201704	CMCC	7	Brindisi - Lecce	bus			42.6	0
Zadar	201704	CMCC	1	Lecce - Rome	train			580	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	2	Rome - Split	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	3	Split - Zadar	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	4	Zadar - Spit	bus			150	0.02
Zadar	201704	CMCC	5	Spit - Rome	plane			405	0.05
Zadar	201704	CMCC	6	Rome - Brindisi	plane			480	0.07
Zadar	201704	CMCC	7	Brindisi - Lecce	bus			42.6	0

Table 2: Example of some entries in the consolidated dataset. The emitted CO₂ is given in tons and the distance in km, while the car_occupancy field is empty since the reported transport mean for this specific leg was not a car.

The database included a total of 337 rows, or voyage legs. They correspond to 25 unique travelers (among PP members and Guests), who performed a total of 59 travels funded by the GUTTA project.

This database could be easily analyzed in various ways, as described in the following section.

4. Results

The data collected and processed as in Sect.3 were used for an automated analysis via a bespoke developed python code. A minimal set of libraries (pandas and numpy) were used, and code development occurred via a jupyter notebook.

First, some overall statistics are provided in Sect.4.1, then an insight into the use of transportation means is given in Sect.4.2, and finally the attribution of emissions to specific events or PPs is done in Sect.4.3.

4.1 Overall statistics

During the GUTTA project (including its preparatory meeting), people funded by the project reported a total of 59 return voyages, each one consisting, on the average, of 6 legs (median value). PPs travelled for a total of about 102,000 km, more than twice the Earth circumference, emitting a total of about 11.6 tons CO₂, at a mean intensity of 105 g CO₂/km. The amount of CO₂

emitted corresponds to the to the carbon footprint of an Italian citizen along a period of about 19 months⁴ [2].

4.2 Transportation means

Plane and cars were the most frequently used transportation means: they accounted for 81% of the total covered distance and 94% of total CO₂ emissions. Train and bus voyages altogether accounted for about 13% of the total covered distance but just 5% of the total emissions (Table 3). However, the mean carbon intensity of the travels results to be lower than car’s one.

<i>Transport mean</i>	<i>Σ distance [km]</i>	<i>Σ CO₂ [t]</i>	<i><cDIST> [grCO₂/km]</i>
<i>plane</i>	64,893	8.98	138
<i>car</i>	17,188	1.94	120
<i>train</i>	10,989	0.40	31
<i>ferry</i>	6,237	0.11	16
<i>bus</i>	2,454	0.16	73
Σ	101,762	11.59	<> 105

Table 3: Overall metrics of the GUTTA travels: distance travelled, CO₂ emissions, and emission intensity, grouped by transport mean.

4.3. Partners and Events

The attribution of the emissions to the various GUTTA partners and events is visualized by means of a Sankey plot as displayed in Figure 3.

It shows the apportionment of travel CO₂ emissions across PPs and events. The most impacting events were the KOM (“201903 Lecce”) and the final workshop (“202205 Lecce”). In both events, the carbon footprint appears to be critically influenced by emissions coming from the “Guests” category. These were non-GUTTA Partners members taking part to the events. Guests were, in fact, the most emitting category overall – maybe because they were often coming from non-Programme areas and thus likely covering larger distances by plane to reach the event venues. On the other hand, among the PPs, CMCC (which was the LP and, as such, present at all official project events) and UniZd were responsible for most of the GHG emissions.

Instead, the bubble plot in Figure 4 focusses on the distribution of CO₂ emissions depending on both PPs and events, encoding the mean carbon intensity as a color and the total carbon footprint of the event as bubble radius.

⁴ Using a value of 7.2 tons of CO₂e, emitted per person in 2019, cf. Fig. III-11.3 in the cited report on BES.

Figure 4 shows that the KOM, the final workshop and the Zagreb steering committee meeting in 2019 included the most energy-inefficient trips done by Guests. The final workshop was the second most impacting event but, at the same time, one of the most carbon-efficient ones. CMCC and UniZd, while being the most impacting PPs in terms of absolute number of emissions, were the most carbon efficient PPs. UniZd score was the best one and benefitted from several ferry legs due to field campaigns for onboard measurements. CSA and Guests performed the least efficient travels.

Figure 3: Sankey plot for the distribution of CO2 emissions across PPs and GUTTA project events.

Figure 4: Bubble plot showing CO₂ emissions and emissions intensity by PP and event. For each PP and event E, the size of bubble in position (E, PP) is proportional to the sum of CO₂ emissions, while its colour encodes the average cDIST. The bubbles in the last row encode the sum of CO₂ emissions and mean cDIST of a specific event, while the last column shows data aggregated by PP.

5. Conclusions

The GUTTA project aimed at contributing to reduction of the carbon emissions of cross-border maritime transport between Italy and Croatia. As technical results critically depend on people’s motivations, the project proposal’s authors considered useful to raise the awareness of the partnership about the own carbon footprint.

Thus, during the project implementation phase, the LP of GUTTA developed a protocol for collecting information about the travels funded by the project, and an objective methodology to analyze them.

A total of 59 travels were reported, corresponding to an emission of 11.6 tons CO₂. These were analyzed in relation to the organizations the travelers belonged to, the actual event attended, and the transportation means used.

After the project-external guests, the LP produced the heaviest carbon footprint, which is understandable given that it attended most of the GUTTA events. However, as the emissions per distance are considered, the LP was the second most efficient Partner. Plane and car were the most used transportation means. The more carbon efficient ferry, train and bus were used for less than one sixth of the total distance covered by travelers. This is partially due to the limited

diffusion of the railway network in Croatia and the limited availability of maritime cross-border links, especially off-season. However, it also indicates a specific potential for greening the carbon footprint of project members.

It should also be noted that the PP were informed since the project beginning that their footprint was going to be monitored for the sake of the present deliverable but were at that time generally unaware about the footprint of specific transport solutions. This is the specific gap filled by the present deliverable.

Bibliography

[1] N. Withers, “Science Focus,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencefocus.com/planet-earth/how-much-does-human-breathing-contribute-to-climate-change/>

[2] Relazione sugli indicatori di Benessere Equo e Sostenibile 2022 (BES), Dipartimento del Tesoro, Ministero dell’Economia e delle Finanze, https://www.dt.mef.gov.it/it/news/2022/bes_2022.html

Appendix A

Overview metrics of the events reported.

The 337 rows in the original dataset⁵ were, at first, grouped by PP and event date and destination, then, for each group, the sum of emitted CO2 tons, the total number of traveled kilometers, and the mean carbon intensity indicator (cDist) were computed.

Project Partner	Event date and destination	$\Sigma CO2$ [t]	$\Sigma Distance$ [km]	<cDIST> [grCO2/km]
AdSP	201910 Zagreb	0.45	3,278	136

⁵ Available at ...

	202205 Lecce	0.06	616	100
	All events	0.51	3,894	118
All PPs	201611 Venice	0.07	2,060	34
	201704 Zadar	0.63	4,868	159
	201903 Lecce	4.00	31,657	118
	201905 Cruise	0.07	4,659	24
	201905 Portorose	0.12	577	200
	201909 Cruise	0	764	0
	201909 Venice	0.08	797	99
	201910 Cruise	0.17	2,051	58
	201910 Zagreb	2.10	17,325	119
	201911 Zadar	0.11	572	200
	201912 Split	0.17	854	199
	202203 Opatija	0.97	8,653	94
	202205 Cruise	0.06	1292	67
	202205 Lecce	3.02	25,327	103
	202206 Bari	0.02	306	65
		All events	11.59	101,766
CMCC	201611 Venice	0.07	2,060	34
	201704 Zadar	0.51	4,296	119
	201903 Lecce	0.24	1,671	157
	201910 Zagreb	0.81	6,513	121
	202203 Opatija	0.71	6,065	88
	202206 Bari	0.02	306	65
		All events	2.35	20,912
CSA	201704 Zadar	0.11	572	200
	201903 Lecce	0.58	4,872	107
	201905 Portorose	0.12	577	200
	201909 Venice	0.08	797	99
	201911 Zadar	0.11	572	200
	201912 Split	0.17	854	199
	202203 Opatija	0.03	344	83
	202205 Lecce	0.33	2,395	87

	All events	1.54	10,984	147
Guests	201903 Lecce	1.75	13,865	128
	201910 Zagreb	0.73	5,246	170
	202203 Opatija	0.03	344	83
	202205 Lecce	1.24	11,300	128
	All events	3.75	30,755	127
MMPI	201903 Lecce	0.66	4,782	115
	202203 Opatija	0.08	688	116
	202205 Lecce	0.32	2,370	99
	All events	1.06	7,840	110
Unizd	201903 Lecce	0.78	6,465	83
	201905 Cruise	0.07	4,659	24
	201909 Cruise	0	764	0
	201910 Cruise	0.17	2,051	58
	201910 Zagreb	0.11	2,288	50
	202203 Opatija	0.12	1,212	100
	202205 Cruise	0.06	1,292	67
	202205 Lecce	1.06	8,645	102
	All events	2.38	27,378	60

Table 4: Input data used for producing both Fig.3 and Fig.4.